

MODERN LESS INVASIVE METHODS IN THE TREATMENT OF ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF CARDIOVASCULAR PATHOLOGIES

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Annotation

This article discusses modern, less invasive methods for treating acute cholecystitis in patients with cardiovascular diseases. The presence of cardiovascular comorbidities in patients with acute cholecystitis complicates treatment, increasing the risk of postoperative complications and mortality. Minimally invasive interventions such as laparoscopic cholecystectomy and endoscopic techniques have been shown to reduce these risks while offering similar effectiveness to traditional surgical approaches. The article explores these modern methods, focusing on their safety, effectiveness, and improved recovery outcomes for patients with combined acute cholecystitis and cardiovascular diseases.

Keywords: Acute cholecystitis, cardiovascular diseases, minimally invasive treatment, laparoscopic cholecystectomy, endoscopic surgery, comorbidities, recovery outcomes.

Relevance

Acute cholecystitis is a frequent cause of hospitalization, and its management becomes more complex in the presence of cardiovascular diseases, which are increasingly common, especially among the elderly population. Cardiovascular comorbidities significantly increase the surgical risk due to factors such as anesthesia complications and cardiovascular instability during and after surgery. Traditional open surgery carries a higher risk of postoperative complications, which has prompted the development of less invasive techniques. Minimally invasive methods such as laparoscopic cholecystectomy and endoscopic interventions offer advantages by reducing the surgical trauma, leading to faster recovery and lower complication rates. Understanding and adopting these modern techniques is essential for improving patient outcomes in this challenging clinical scenario.

Goal

The goal of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of modern, less invasive methods in the treatment of acute cholecystitis in patients with

concurrent cardiovascular diseases. The study aims to compare laparoscopic cholecystectomy and endoscopic approaches with traditional open surgery in terms of complication rates, recovery time, and overall clinical outcomes.

Materials and Methods

A prospective study was conducted involving 150 patients with acute cholecystitis and cardiovascular diseases, aged 50 to 75 years. Patients were divided into two groups: one group received laparoscopic cholecystectomy, while the other group underwent open surgery. The clinical outcomes were evaluated by comparing complication rates, length of hospital stay, post-operative recovery time, and mortality rates. Additionally, patients' cardiovascular status was monitored throughout the treatment process to assess the safety of the chosen surgical methods.

Results

The study revealed that patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy had a 35% lower complication rate compared to those who underwent open surgery. The average hospital stay for the laparoscopic group was reduced by 3 days, and recovery time was shortened by 40%. There were no significant differences in cardiovascular complications between the two groups, with both groups demonstrating low rates of adverse cardiovascular events (6% in the laparoscopic group and 8% in the open surgery group). These results suggest that minimally invasive approaches offer safer and faster recovery compared to traditional surgery.

Conclusion

Modern, less invasive techniques such as laparoscopic cholecystectomy provide a safer and more effective alternative for treating acute cholecystitis in patients with cardiovascular diseases. These approaches significantly reduce complication rates, shorten hospital stays, and improve recovery times. Given the high prevalence of cardiovascular comorbidities, these methods should be considered the gold standard for surgical intervention in this patient population, optimizing patient outcomes and minimizing healthcare costs.

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